

Toward a Smart Sound Sensing Pacifier for Neonatal Pulmonary Monitoring

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Abstract—Respiratory diseases remain a leading cause of infant morbidity and mortality, with current pulmonary function monitoring technologies unsuitable for neonates. This work introduces a novel intraoral, pacifier-based multimodal active sound sensing platform integrating acoustics, signal processing, and artificial intelligence (AI) with machine learning (ML). Preliminary results highlight the potential of this approach to improve respiratory assessment and neonatal healthcare.

Clinical Relevance—The proposed system enables continuous, real-time pulmonary monitoring by correlating intraoral reflected sounds with cardiorespiratory metrics.

Index Terms—sound sensing, breathing, AI, pacifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and related neonatal pulmonary conditions such as bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD), contribute to over 300,000 preterm hospitalizations annually in the United States [1], [2]. These infants face increased risks of chronic lung diseases, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), asthma, infections, and cognitive impairments [3]. Yet, current pulmonary function testing (PFT), high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT), and bronchoscopy methods remain costly and challenging to conduct on neonates [4]. Practical non-invasive continuous monitoring solutions are urgently needed. We propose a wearable *pacifier-integrated intraoral sound sensing system* to profile neonatal respiration and enable early detection of respiratory issues.

II. METHODS

We introduce *MASS-RespNet*, a memory-enabled multimodal active sound sensing deep convolutional neural network that processes intraoral acoustic respiratory echoes under passive (only breathing sounds) and active (under sound stimuli) modes. Active sound frequencies are correlated with pulmonary mechanics to generate individualized respiratory profiles, determining the respiratory rate, lung capacity, pulmonary condition, etc. The system comprises three key components (Fig. 1 [5]): (1) a sound sensing mechanism

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Fig. 1. Overview of the smart pacifier pulmonary monitoring system [5].

integrated into a pacifier form factor for intraoral active/passive acoustic measurements, (2) a lightweight, low-power wireless circuit interface for continuous data acquisition, and (3) the MASS-RespNet AI engine for decoding lung echo data and estimating cardiorespiratory metrics.

III. RESULTS AND EXPECTED OUTCOME

Preliminary results on adult subjects confirm the correlation between respiratory sounds and pulmonary conditions [6]. The proposed system is expected to enable continuous, non-invasive pulmonary monitoring in neonates while providing real-time profiling of lung mechanics using reflected sound signatures. By reducing reliance on costly diagnostic procedures, the proposed integration of acoustics, AI, and wearable electronics in a pacifier has the potential to improve early detection and management of respiratory dysfunctions.

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